

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Software, Policy, and Processes

Policy Updates relevant to SMD

There are new policies that have been released or developed relevant for SMD related to policy.

While the policies have been released, the processes around the policy are still being updated. Thank you for your patience as we work through these processes.

- [SPD-41a: Scientific Information Policy for SMD](#)
- [NPR 2210: Release of NASA Software](#)
- [Draft Research Access Plan for NASA](#)

SPD-41a: Scientific Information Policy

Summary of Major Policy Updates in SPD-41a related to software:

- Research software are shared at the time of publication or the end of the funding award.
- Unrestricted mission software is developed openly.
- During reviews, peer reviewed software is viewed as having commensurate value as peer review publications
- Software packages should be indexed in the NASA software catalog
- When released, software should be released with a permissive license

The policy is forward looking applying to ROSES23 and missions that have not passed KDP-B by March 2023. It is not applicable to restricted software. SPD-41a is compliant with the updated draft Research Access Plan.

Updates to NPR 2210: NASA Software Release

NPR2210.2E released in June 2023, but it will still take some time to integrate into existing processes.

Highlights of updates related to SMD:

- Software developed solely for scientific publications will be treated as other Science and Technical Information.
- Projects can go through the Software Release process at the start and then be fully developed in the open.
- Additional licenses than NOSA can be used. Consult with OGC on appropriate licenses.
- NASA personnel can contribute to work-related open source projects with approval from their manager.

See [Policy](#) for full details. Many groups (OCE, OCS, OGC, SRA, STI, Export Control, and OCSDO) are working closely to update the processes.

STRIVES

JoAnne Calhoun

2024 NASA Software Workshop STI Services, STRIVES, and Software

Tuesday, May 7, 2024

Scientific and Technical Information
Information, Data, & Analytics Services (IDAS)
Office of the Chief Information Officer

STI Compliance and Distribution Services

NASA STI Services

The Agency-wide STI Compliance and Distribution Services collects, organizes, manages, disseminates, and provides for long-term retention of NASA's STI.

What is STI?

NASA STI is defined as the results (facts, analyses, and conclusions) of basic and applied scientific, technical, and related engineering research and development. STI also includes management, industrial, and economic information relevant to this research.

NASA has a responsibility to ensure the scientific and technical information (STI) it releases is technically accurate, is appropriately marked for any restrictions, and does not violate any export control and intellectual property federal laws and statutes.

The NASA Scientific and Technical Information (STI) Discovery System (STRIVES) process is the dissemination or release approval process by which NASA also determines which restrictions, if any, need to be placed on a document.

Benefits of the STI STRIVES Process:

- Determines how a document may be released or restricted
- Provides a review of export-controlled content and intellectual property concerns
- Increases public access to NASA's scientific publications and digital scientific data

Approval is crucial to ensuring:

- Technical accuracy and professional quality
- That management has approved the document for release
- That restricted information is not released publicly

When is a STRIVES review required?

A review is done prior to releasing STI internally where foreign nationals may be present or disseminating externally to a public/non-NASA audience.

Who reviews the STI?

The Agency requires a least four different STRIVES approvers to review and clear STI for release.

The STRIVES submission routes to the following approvers:

- ✓ Management Approver (*Acceptability for release*)
- ✓ Center STI Staff (*Quality review*)
- ✓ Center Patent Counsel Office (*Copyright, inventions, patents, and third-party content guidance*)
- ✓ Center Export Control Office (*EAR and ITAR*)

Does the STRIVES review requirement apply to all authors?

Civil servants and contractors whose contracts specify the review requirement are required to put their STI through the STRIVES review. Grantee authors do not have the review requirement unless specifically directed by NASA.

Public Access

All NASA-funded researchers (both civil servant and non-civil servant) are required to ensure that copies of NASA-funded peer-reviewed publications are made available in NASA's designated public access repository, [PubSpace](#).

Software and Publications

NPR 2210.1E, Release of NASA Software

Section P.2 Applicability, Section (3) g.

This NPR does not apply to Scientific Research Demonstration Software (as defined in Appendix A) that is developed and used for the purpose of supporting a scientific publication. Such publication-related software may be released with the scientific publication, but, as part of the **NPR 2200.2, Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information, review process for dissemination of scientific and technical information, the author/management is responsible to confirm that the related software meets the requirements set forth in the definition of Scientific Research Demonstration Software.** The ability to distribute such software under NPR 2200.2 does not also permit the inclusion or release of any underlying software that may be related to the subject of the scientific publication, which would still need to be reported and released under NPR 2210.

Appendix A: Definition of Scientific Research Demonstration Software

Scientific Research Demonstration Software - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA's use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software. (*NPR 2210.1E, Release of NASA Software, NPR 2210.1E – Appendix A, https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/npg_img/N_PR_2210_001E_/N_PR_2210_001E_.pdf*)

Scientific Research Demonstration Software and STRIVES

- Scientific Research Demonstration Software
 - Software authored by civil servants only
 - No use of third-party licenses unless permissions granted
 - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2.
 - Not reviewed via the Software Release Process, NPR 2210.1
- **What's not Scientific Research Demonstration Software**
 - Software classified as Class A, B, C, D, or F via the NPR 7150.2 2 NASA Software Engineering Requirements classifications.
 - Software developed for the operations of a mission.
 - Software that would be restricted from release by ITAR, export control, or other security restrictions.
 - Level 0 to Level 1 data processing pipelines or later stage data processing pipelines developed by the mission team.
 - Simulation software for a mission developed by the mission team.
 - Software developed for the archiving and distribution of NASA data.
 - Commercial software
 - Reviewed via the Software Release Process, NPR 2210.1
- STRIVES is not currently designed to handle the inclusion of Scientific Research Demonstration Software as supplementary information with a publication. This will require system engineering changes and defining the process. Currently, STRIVES can review publications, but we cannot software files until all the system and process modifications are made.

STI Information

- Main STI SharePoint site: [STI Compliance and Distribution Services](#)
- STI Handbook: <https://nasa.sharepoint.com/sites/NASASTIProgram/SitePages/STI-Policy-&-Guidance.aspx>
- Join STI User Group: [STRIVES and STI Repository \(NTRS\) User Group](#)
- Become member of the STI Communications Distribution List: [STI Communications Distribution List](#)

STRIVES and NTRS

- STRIVES: <https://strives.nasa.gov>
- STRIVES Resources: <https://nasa.sharepoint.com/sites/NASASTIProgram/SitePages/STRIVES.aspx>
- STI Repository (NTRS): <https://ntrs.nasa.gov>

Policies:

- NPD 2200.1: [Management of NASA Scientific and Technical Information](#)
- NPR 2200.2: [Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information](#)
- NPR 2210.1E, [Release of NASA Software](#)
- NPD 2230.1, [Research Data and Publication Access](#)

NPR 7120.5 and the Software Engineering Handbook

Scott Tashakkor

NPR 7150.2 and NASA's SWE Handbook

Scott B. Tashakkor, P.E., NESC Deputy Tech Fellow for Software
SMD Software Workshop
May 7, 2024

What Is Software Engineering?

Software Engineering is not programming!

“a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation and maintenance of software; that is, the application of engineering to software” IEEE

The term was coined by Margaret Hamilton in 1963-1964, director of the Software Engineering Division of the MIT Instrumentation Laboratory, which developed on-board flight software for NASA's Apollo program.

“It was a memorable day when one of the most respected hardware gurus explained to everyone in a meeting that he agreed with me that the process of building software should also be considered an engineering discipline, just like with hardware.” Margaret Hamilton

NASA's Software Definition (From IEEE)

Software is defined as:

- (1) computer programs, procedures and possibly associated documentation and data pertaining to the operation of a computer system
- (2) all or a part of the programs, procedures, rules, and associated documentation of an information processing system
- (3) program or set of programs used to run a computer
- (4) all or part of the programs which process or support the processing of digital information
- (5) part of a product that is the computer program or the set of computer programs

This definition

- Software developed by NASA,
- Software developed for NASA,
- Software maintained by or for NASA,
- Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) software,
- Government off-the-shelf (GOTS) software,
- Modified off-the-shelf (MOTS) software,
- Reused software,
- Auto-generated code,

- Embedded software,
- The software executed on processors embedded in programmable logic devices (see NASA-HDBK-4008, Programmable Logic Devices (PLD) Handbook),
- Legacy software,

Software Is Not All the Same

flight software \neq *Non-flight software*

engineering software \neq *general purpose software*

safety critical software \neq *non-safety critical software*

... and it shouldn't be treated the same!

NPD 1000.0 Strategic Management & Governance Handbook
NPD 1000.3 The NASA Organization
NPD 1000.5 Policy for NASA Acquisition

Governing Documents

Current NASA Software Documentation Tree

(with a few related non-software documents in gray)

Policy

Procedural Requirements

Standards

Handbooks & Guidebooks

Center Level Directives

Purpose of the NASA Software Engineering Requirements, NPR 7150.2

- Software engineering is a **core capability** for NASA's missions and supporting infrastructure.
- **Support the implementation of NASA's policies**
- **Provide a minimal set of requirements**
- **Support NASA programs and projects in accomplishing their planned goals**

NPR 7150.2 History

Nov 2004 –
Original

Nov 2009 – Rev A

Nov 2014 – Rev B

Aug 2019 – Rev C

Mar 2022 – Rev D

Table of Contents

Preface
P.1 Purpose
P.2 Applicability
P.3 Authority
P.4 Applicable Documents and Forms
P.5 Measurement/Verification
P.6 Cancellation

Chapter 1. Introduction
1.1 Overview
1.2 Hierarchy of NASA Software-Related Engineering and
1.3 Document Structure

Chapter 2. Roles, Responsibilities, and Principles Relat
2.1 Roles and Responsibilities
2.2 Principles Related to Tailoring of the Requirements

Chapter 3. Software Management Requirements
3.1 Software Life Cycle Planning
3.2 Software Cost Estimation
3.3 Software Schedules
3.4 Software Training
3.5 Software Classification Assessments
3.6 Software Assurance and Software Independent Verific
3.7 Safety-Critical Software
3.8 Automatic Generation of Software Source Code
3.9 Software Development Processes and Practices
3.10 Software Reuse
3.11 Software Cybersecurity
3.12 Software Bi-Directional Traceability

Chapter 4. Software Engineering (Life Cycle) Require
4.1 Software Requirements
4.2 Software Architecture
4.3 Software Design
4.4 Software Implementation
4.5 Software Testing
4.6 Software Operations, Maintenance, and Retirement

Chapter 5. Supporting Software Life Cycle Requirem
5.1 Software Configuration Management
5.2 Software Risk Management
5.3 Software Peer Reviews/Inspections
5.4 Software Measurements

5.5 Software Non-conformance or Defect Management

Chapter 6. Recommended Software Documentation Contents
6.1 Software Engineering Product
6.2 Software Engineering Product Content

List of Appendices
Appendix A. Definitions
Appendix B. Acronyms
Appendix C. Requirements Mapping Matrix
Appendix D. Software Classifications
Appendix E. References

List of Figures
Figure 1. NASA Software Classification Structure

List of Tables
Table 1. Bi-directional traceability by software classification
Table 2. Requirements Mapping Matrix

About NASA's Software Engineering Requirements (NPR 7150.2)

- The NASA Office of the Chief Engineer is responsible for the NPR
- The NPR shall be applied to all software development, maintenance, operations, management, acquisition, and assurance activities
- Includes engineering and assurance requirements
- Requirements are levied on Center organizations as well as projects
 - Applicability of requirements is determined through the use of a NASA-wide definition of software classes
- To find the document online go to NASA Online Directives Information System (NODIS)
 - http://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/main_lib.html
 - Look for NPR 7150.2

Directive ID	Subject	Expiration Date
NPD 7010.1L	Processing Legislative Proposals	January 29, 2023
NPD 7100.10F	Curation of Institutional Scientific Collections (Revalidated w/Change 1)	May 26, 2026
NPR 7100.1B	Protection of Human Research Subjects	February 15, 2024
NPD 7100.8F	Protection of Human Research Subjects	April 29, 2024
NPR 7120.10A	Technical Standards for NASA Programs and Projects	July 21, 2022
NPR 7120.11A	NASA Health and Medical Technical Authority (HMTA) Implementation	September 8, 2025
NPD 7120.4E	NASA Engineering and Program/Project Management Policy	June 26, 2022
NPR 7120.5F	NASA Space Flight Program and Project Management Requirements	August 3, 2026
NPD 7120.6A	Knowledge Policy for Programs and Projects	December 16, 2024
NPR 7120.7A	NASA Information Technology Program and Project Management Requirements	August 17, 2025
NPR 7120.8A	NASA Research and Technology Program and Project Management Requirements (Updated w/Change 2)	September 14, 2023
NPR 7123.1C	NASA Systems Engineering Processes and Requirements (w/Change 2)	February 14, 2025
NPR 7150.2C	NASA Software Engineering Requirements	August 2, 2024
NPD 7170.1	Use of Human Research Genetic Testing	February 22, 2023
NPD 7330.1I	Approval Authorities for Facility Projects (Revalidated w/Change 1 on September 23, 2021)	January 6, 2026
NPD 7410.1H	Management of Contract and Grant Support Services Obtained from External Sources (Revalidated 8/14/2018)	August 27, 2023
NPD 7500.1D	Program and Project Life-Cycle Logistics Support Policy	June 2, 2022
NPR 7500.2	NASA Technology Transfer Requirements	July 19, 2022
NPD 7620.1I	Official Names for Major NASA Projects (Revalidated w/Change 2)	February 14, 2025
NPR 7900.3D	Aircraft Operations Management	May 1, 2023
NPD 7900.4D	NASA Aircraft Operations Management, Updated with Change 1, March 10, 2015	December 7, 2022

Visual Overview of NPR 7150.2

30 “Institutional” Requirements (Chapter 2)

NPR 7150.2

Applicable to All Classifications

OC	SM	Center	Director/Delegate(s)	Measure for Improvement	Maintains contributor list
Lead Software Engineering Initiative	Lead Software Assurance and Safety Initiative	Director/Delegate(s)	software engineering capability	Measure for Improvement	Maintains contributor list
Benchmark Center’s Capabilities against this NPR	Benchmark Center’s SWA and SW Safety Capabilities	Establish and execute software processes	Establish and maintain software cost repo	Ensure Proper transfer of software	
Benchmark Center Mapping Matrices	Review Center’s Mapping Matrices	Comply with NPR per Classification in Appendix C	Contribute to Agency PAL (Process Asset Library)	Contract Officer: Ensure NPR is on contract	
Authorize Compliance Appraisals	Authorize Appriasals against requirements	Report project status	Define content of SW documentation	Tech Authority: Assess against NPR	
Provide Software Engineering Training	Provide Software Assurance Training	Maintain list of projects	Ensure Government rights to Software	OCE, SMA, OCIO: agree on tailoring	
Maintain Process Asset Library (PAL)	Makes Decisions on Tailoring IVV Rqmt	Establish and maintain software Metrics	Ensure reuse software conforms to policies	Project Manager: Update plans per Classification	

100 NPR Requirements* - *Applicable Based on Classification*

NPR 7150.2

Software Management (Chapter

Lifecycle (Chapter

Lifecycle Support-

3) Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MC/DC	Verify Cyber Protection	4) Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Cyclomatic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Rqmts	Identify CM Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs. Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop, Test Data Upload Procedures	Establish CM Procedures	Analyze Software Measurements
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier Inputs	Record Adversarial Actions	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Reuse/COTS Equally	Maintain CM Records	House Measurement Data
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec Plan (IPEP) if IVV	Perform and Certify as CMMI	Perform Bi-Directional Traceability	Implement, Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops, Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CM Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define Milestones	Store Cost in Repo	Provide IVV Artifacts	Identify Reuse Rqmts	Establish Rqmts	Adhere to Coding Standards	Use Accredited Tools	Deliver Products	Develop Release Procedures	Measure Software Volatility
Developer Report Status	Develop Schedule	Respond to IVV Findings	Evaluate Reusability	Map to System Rqmts	Perform Static Code Analysis	Update Plans	Complete Verification	Participate in Audits	Track Defects
Dev'er Provide Product & Metrics	Regularly Review with Stakeholders	Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety Rqmts	Unit Test	Validate in High-fidelity	Maintain	Determine, Manage Risk	Determine Severity Levels
Developer to Provide Access to Source Code	Dev'ers Report Schedule	Adhere to 8739.8 SWA & SW Safety Std	Identify Cyber Risks	Track Rqmt Changes	Repeat Unit Test	Track Code Coverage Metrics	Archive	Peer Review Rqmts, Plans, Code, Test	Assess reuse, COTS defects
Comply with this NPR	Train	Do Safety-Crit items: SWE-134	Implement Cyber Protection	Track Corrective Actions	Develop VDD	Validate Metrics in Test	Plan CM	Follow Basic Peer Review Process	Assess Process Defects

*Note SWE-220 Cyclomatic Complexity has 2 shalls, counted as 1

Class A&B (All 100)

C (92)

D (64)

E (12)

Requirements

NPR 7150.2

Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MDR	Verify Cyber Protection	Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Cyclomatic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Points	Identify CM Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen Lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop Test Data Upload	Establish CM Procedures	Analyze Software
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier	Record Adversarial	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Reuse/COTS	Maintain CM Records	House Measurement
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec	Perform and Certify as CMM	Perform Bi-Directional	Implement Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops, Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CM Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define	Store Cost in	Provide IVV	Identify Reuse Rqmts	Establish Rqmt	Adhere to	Use Accredited	Deliver Product	Develop Release	Measure
Identify	Identify	Respond to IVV	Evaluate Reusability	Rqmts	Standards for Static	Identify	Complete	Verify	Volatility Track Defects
Report Status Developer Provide	Schedule Regularly	Findings Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety	Code Analysis Unit Test	Validate in	Verification Maintain	Audits Determine, Manage	Determine Severity
Product & Metrics	Stakeholders	Where to	Identify Cyber	Track Rqmt	Repeat Unit Test	Track Code	Archive	Peer Review	Assess reuse, COTS Defect
Developer to Provide Access to Source Code	Secure	SW Safety Std	Identify	Track Correctiv	Develop VDD	Metrics	Plan CM	Code Test Follow Basic Peer Review	Assess Process Defects
Comply with this NPR	Train	Items: SWE-134	Implement Cyber	Track Correctiv Actions	Develop VDD	Validate Metric in Test	Plan CM	Code Test Follow Basic Peer Review	Assess Process Defects

Class F Requirement Applicability (OCIO Authority)

NPR 7150.2

Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MC/IVV	Verify Cyber Protection	Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Systematic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Points	Identify CM Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs. Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop, Test Data Upload Procedures	Establish CM Procedures	Analyze Software Measurements
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier Inputs	Record Adversarial Actions	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Review/COTS Equally	Maintain CM Records	House Measurement Data
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec Plan (IPEP) if IVV	Perform and Certify as CMMI	Perform Bi-Directional Traceability	Implement, Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops, Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CM Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define Milestones	Store Cost in Reports	Provide IVV Artifacts	Identify Reuse Rqmts	Establish Rqmts	Adhere to Coding Standards	Use Accredited Tools	Deliver Products	Develop Release Procedures	Measure Software Volatility
Developer Report Status	Develop Schedule	Respond to IVV Findings	Evaluate Reusability	Map to System Rqmts	Perform Static Code Analysis	Update Plans	Complete Verification	Participate in Audits	Track Defects
Dev'er Provide Product & Metrics	Regularly Review with Stakeholders	Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety Rqmts	Unit Test	Validate in High-fidelity	Maintain	Determine, Manage Risk	Determine Severity Level
Developer to Provide Access to Source Code	Dev'ers Report Schedule	Adhere to 8739.8 SWA & SW Safety Std	Identify Cyber Risks	Track Rqmt Changes	Repeat Unit Test	Track Code Coverage Metrics	Archive	Peer Review Rqmts, Plans Code Test	Assess reuse, COTS defects
Comply with this NPR	Train	Identify Safety-Crit items: SWE-134	Implement Cyber Protection	Track Corrective Actions	Develop VDD	Validate Metrics in Test	Plan CM	Follow Basic Peer Review Process	Assess Process Defects

Software Engineering Handbook

NPR
7150.2A

NPR
7150.2B

NPR
7150.2C

NPR
7150.2D

- Guidance material to help the NASA workforce implement the software engineering requirements in NPR 7150.2 and promote best practices across the Agency in software engineering.
- Addresses topics of interest identified by the Software Engineering community of practice
- Provides guidance for all of the software engineering requirements contained in NASA's NPR 7150.2, plus topics
- Guidance material includes requirement specific guidance, rationale, examples, best practices, lessons learned, references, tools and templates

<https://swebh.nasa.gov/>

Handbook Version Transition Page

NASA Software Engineering Handbook
Content based on NPR7150.2D

NASA ENGINEERING NETWORK

A. Introduction B. Institutional Requirements C. Project Software Requirements D. Topics E. Tools, References, and Terms F. SPAN (NASA Only) Search

Dashboard

Book A. Introduction

Created by Bruce J Guy, last modified by Haign, Fred Douglas. (HQ-KA000)[PEROT] on Apr 15, 2022

1. Welcome 2. SWEHB Introduction 3. Title Material 4. Resources 5. Accessing Other Versions of SWEHB

The version of the handbook that you are viewing is noted in the header image. Clicking on this image, while on any page of the SWEHBVD, will take you back to the Introduction page for this version.

To access other versions of the Software Engineering Handbook use the links below:

- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2A](#)
- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2B](#)
- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2C](#)
- You are already in the Software Engineering and Software Assurance Handbook from NPR 7150.2D

Four versions of the NASA Software Engineering and Assurance Handbook, NASA-HDBK-2203 are available for use (see Tab 5 to access the versions of the handbook)

- The original version of the handbook - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2A. NPR 7150.2A had an effective date of November 19, 2009, to the expiration date of November 19, 2014.
- Revision A - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2B. NPR 7150.2B had an effective date of November 19, 2014, to the expiration date of August 2, 2019.
- Revision B - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2C and the requirements in the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety standard, NASA-STD-8739.8A. NPR 7150.2C had an effective date of August 2, 2019, to the expiration date of August 2, 2024. NASA-STD-8739.8A ²⁷⁸ has an effective date of June 10, 2020.
- Revision C - Addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2D, and the requirements in the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety standard, NASA-STD-8739.8A. NPR 7150.2D had an effective date of 03/08/2022, to the expiration date of 03/08/2027. NASA-STD-8739.8A ²⁷⁸ has an effective date of June 10, 2020.

NPR 7150.2D is the latest version of the NASA Software Engineering Requirements.

NASA-STD-8739.8A is the latest version of the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety Standard

5.1 SWE History

The SWE History Summary includes all SWE numbers and their history of use in all versions of the Software Engineering Handbook.

Click [SWE History](#) to view.

Remember...

- **NPRs and Standards (including NPR 7150.2) are not intended to be “one size fits all documents”**
 - **They have built-in tailoring**
 - **Software Classification (Class A, B, C, D, E, or F)**
 - **Tailoring of the Software Classification requirements**
 - **There is a level of compliance and rigor specified that is associated with the class of the software to be built or acquired**
 - ***Part of your job as is to carefully consider what tailoring is necessary and build time into your schedule to complete it***
- **There are tailoring procedures via Center and HQ Engineering Technical Authority (ETA)**

Use good software engineering and software assurance judgement on which requirements should be implemented by your project

Questions

Additional information can be found at

<https://nen.nasa.gov/web/software>

<https://swebb.nasa.gov/>

<https://sma.nasa.gov/sma-disciplines/software-assurance>

<https://nsc.nasa.gov/SMAToolbox/>

<https://software.nasa.gov>

<https://open.nasa.gov>

<https://developer.nasa.gov>

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Software Release Authority

Chris Copelan
Kimberly Minafra

National Aeronautics and Space
Administration

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Navigating the Process of SOFTWARE RELEASE

Kimberly Minafra

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Authority

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NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software”

Purpose

The NASA Procedural Requirements (NPR) establishes procedures and responsibilities for the reporting, review, assessment, and release of software created by, or for, NASA. These procedures reinforce that NASA software is reported and released, both internally and externally, according to law and NASA policies, with appropriate restrictions on the use and redistribution of the software. The unrestricted release of NASA software, (defined in Appendix A), is prohibited.

Applicability

This NPR is applicable to NASA Headquarters and Centers, including Component Facilities, including JPL to the extent required by its contract.

NASA
Procedural
Requirements

NPR 2210.1E
Effective Date: June 14, 2023
Expiration Date: June 14, 2028

COMPLIANCE IS MANDATORY FOR NASA EMPLOYEES

Release of NASA Software

Responsible Office: Space Technology Mission Directorate

Table of Contents

Preface

- P.1 Purpose
- P.2 Applicability
- P.3 Authority
- P.4 Applicable Documents and Forms
- P.5 Measurement/Verification
- P.6 Cancellation

Chapter 1. Responsibilities

- 1.1 Technology Transfer Program Executive
- 1.2 General Counsel
- 1.3 Center Export Administrator (CEA)
- 1.4 Center Directors
- 1.5 NASA Inspector General
- 1.6 NASA Chief Information Security Officer (CISO)
- 1.7 Office of Communications
- 1.8 Center Technology Transfer Officer
- 1.9 Center Software Release Authority
- 1.10 Centralized Software Usage Agreement Processing Team
- 1.11 Responsible Center Offices or Projects

- 1.11 Responsible Center Offices or Projects
- 1.10 Centralized Software Usage Agreement Processing Team
- 1.9 Center Software Release Authority
- 1.8 Center Technology Transfer Officer
- 1.7 Office of Communications
- 1.6 NASA Chief Information Security Officer (CISO)
- 1.5 NASA Inspector General

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software” (cont.)

Updates

- Software Tools needed to validate scientific methodology
- Technical journals require such software with publication
- Added new para. g. “Scientific Research Demonstration Software” in P.2 [Applicability]
- Scientific Research Demonstration Software (SRDS)
- Go through narrow definition below
- When requirements are met, such software falls under release of STI under NPR 2200.2

Limitations on ability to release with publication

- Developed for purpose of supporting scientific publication
- Author/Management must confirm software meets requirements
- Release specifically excludes any underlying software related to scientific publication (which must go through NPR 2210 process)

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software” (cont.)

New Software Considerations

Scientific Research Demonstration Software – Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA’s use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software.

- OR-

Software Documentation - Documentation and data pertaining to the development and operation of software and that explains the capabilities of the software or provides operating instructions for using the software to obtain the desired results. Software Documentation may be provided as owner’s manuals, user’s manuals, installation instructions, operating instructions, anomalies, other similar items.

Software Review Process and Procedure

Software Release is the process of taking NASA internal software and disseminating into the economy and the public...

To generate your Software Release request...

- First, submit your New Technology Report (NTR)
 - <https://invention.nasa.gov/>

The Software Release Authority is alerted and connects with the innovator to introduce the process as soon as a NTR case number is assigned.

- Then, submit a request via NASA's Software Release System (SRS)...
 - <https://softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov/>

Software Release Process

Software Release Authority Workflow

Note A – New Technology (NTR) and Software Release Authorization (SRRA) submission required:

- SRA sends email to developers
- Developer submits an NTR/Invention Disclosure (NF1679) to invention.nasa.gov
- Developer creates Software Release System (SRS) package to be reviewed by the SRA before submitting in SRS (softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov) for routing and reviews/approval

Note B – Software Release Types:

- General Public
- Open Source
- U.S. Government Purpose
- U.S. Release Only
- U.S. & Foreign Release

*See Software Release Options document for details

Note C – Reviewers for Approval:

Once release type is determined, initial approval by Software Release Authority starts reviews/approvals that may include:

- Technology Transfer Office
- IT Security Manager
- 508 Compliance Officer
- Software Engineering
- Safety & Mission Assurance (SMA)
- Patent Office/Legal Counsel

Requests for General Purpose Release requires approval from the Center Export Administrator

Note D – Software Usage Agreements:

SUAs are processed by the NASA Stennis SUA Team, however “ special case” request (i.e. Government Purpose, ITAR, etc.) can be handled by Center Software Release Teams.

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software”

Dear “Software Developer,”

“Thank you again for meeting with me today to share more details on whether your [SOFTWARE NAME] is [purely scientific research] and the purpose is [to distribute mathematical models that manipulate input data to detect anomalies and show it] for a paper. Thanks for providing clarity that [SOFTWARE NAME] is being released for the sole purpose of your published paper.

Per the current NPR 2210.1E (attached), please review the definitions cited in excerpts from *Appendix A. Definitions* in the attached NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software,” to confirm what [SOFTWARE NAME] falls under:

Scientific Research Demonstration Software - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA’s use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software.

- OR -

Software Documentation - Documentation and data pertaining to the development and operation of software and that explains the capabilities of the software or provides operating instructions for using the software to obtain the desired results. Software Documentation may be provided as owner’s manuals, user’s manuals, installation instructions, operating instructions, anomalies, other similar items.

Software Documentation may include design details, algorithms, processes, procedures, rules, flow charts, formulae, and related information that would enable particular NASA software, or functional equivalent thereof, to be reproduced or created. Premature release of such information may jeopardize intellectual property protection and commercialization of the software to which it relates. **Thus, it is advisable that such information is not released unless the Patent or IP Counsel has approved the software for release.**

Per section P.2 Applicability, see the following:

g. This NPR does not apply to Scientific Research Demonstration Software (as defined in Appendix A) that is developed and used for the purpose of supporting a scientific publication. Such publication-related software may be released with the scientific publication, but, as part of the NPR 2200.2, Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information, review process for dissemination of scientific and technical information, the author/management is responsible to confirm that the related software meets the requirements set forth in the definition of Scientific Research Demonstration Software. **The ability to distribute such software under NPR 2200.2 does not also permit the inclusion or release of any underlying software that may be related to the subject of the scientific publication, which would still need to be reported and released under NPR 2210.**

h. **This NPR does not apply to computer databases, websites, or software documentation**, as defined in Appendix A unless such documentation discloses software source code.

If the above definitions (per the NPR, attached) confirm applicability for release under the NPR, we will continue with the process of completing our review in the Software Release System, for final approvals.

What Is the Software Release System (SRS)?

The SRS is the latest innovation designed to prepare your software for release. The system:

- Provides developers with a single platform to ready their software for release to the users who need it
- Employs a simple online questionnaire to replace multiple forms used previously
- Allows software packages to be reviewed concurrently by all necessary reviewers

Previous process

Streamlined Review Cycle of SRS

NASA Software Release System: Getting Started

- Log in at <https://softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov>
- The SRS will give you three options to select.
- During the review, you can track the progress on the Developer Dashboard

Welcome to the NASA Software Release System.

The Software Release System (SRS) will allow Agency software developers to generate and submit software release documents such as the Software Release Request Authorization (SRRRA) and the Compliance Matrix in an automated fashion. The SRS will allow Agency SRAs to then easily route these software release documents for review with the added ability to perform parallel routing, use of time based reminders, tracking, and reporting to effectively manage the software release processes at their centers.

[Submit New Release Request](#)

[Learn about SRS](#)

[Go To Request Dashboard](#)

Who reviews my software? And what is their role?

Technology Transfer Office

- Screen request/coordinate approval and make commercialization determination

Office of Patent Counsel

- Determines IP ownership, copyrights, software provenance, and reviews 3rd party code license

508 Compliance

- Determines if software is safe and accessible for people with disabilities.

NPR 7150.2 Compliance

- NASA Software Engineering Requirements

Export Control/ IT Security

- Ensures software is safe to share with external entities
-

Release Categories

<https://software.nasa.gov>

Release Types

- US/Government Purpose Only
 - US and Foreign
 - Beta Test
 - General Public Purpose
 - Open Source
- (also, on <https://code.nasa.gov/>)

**All, but Open Source require a Software Usage Agreement (SUA) for requestors.*

Resources within Software Release (at Ames)

Software Release Authority	Kimberly Minafra	kimberly.minafra@nasa.gov
New Technology Report	Mank Ahluwalia	manka.ahluwalia@nasa.gov
Office of Patent Counsel	Rob Padilla Meredith Blasingame	robert.m.padilla@nasa.gov meredith.k.Blasingame@nasa.gov
Technology Transfer Office Chief	Kimberly Hines	kimberly.k.hines@nasa.gov
508 Compliance	Gulsum Oz	oz.gulsum@nasa.gov
Export Control Review	Taylor Rayburn	taylor.d.rayburn@nasa.gov
IT Security	Ernest Lopez	ernest.m.lopez@nasa.gov
NPR 7150.2 & STD	Bob Duffy	robert.a.duffy@nasa.gov

The NASA SRA process as it relates to open source workflows developed for GeneLab data processing

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

SMD Software Workshop, 5/7/2024

Lauren Sanders, Ph.D. on behalf of:

Barbara Novak, Ph.D.

NASA GeneLab Data Processing Lead

Contractor: BMSIS

Contact: barbara.a.novak@nasa.gov

Biological & Physical Sciences

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nasa / GeneLab_Data_Processing Public https://github.com/nasa/GeneLab_Data_Processing Edit Pins

README.md

Open Science for Life in Space

GeneLab_Data_Processing

About

The NASA GeneLab Data Processing team and Analysis Working Group members have created standard pipelines for processing omics data from spaceflight and space-relevant experiments. This repository contains the processing pipelines that have been standardized to date for the assay types indicated below. Each subdirectory in this repository holds current and previous pipeline versions for the respective assay type, including detailed descriptions and processing instructions as well as the exact processing commands used to generate processed data for datasets hosted in the [GeneLab Data Repository](#).

Assay Types

Click on an assay type below for data processing information.

- Create GeneLab Reference Annotations
- Amplicon Sequencing
 - Illumina
 - 454 and Ion-Torrent
- Metagenomics
 - Removing human reads
 - Illumina
- (bulk) RNAseq
- single cell RNAseq

SRS Process

Utilizing the Workflow

1. [Install Nextflow and Singularity](#)
 - 1a. [Install Nextflow](#)
 - 1b. [Install Singularity](#)
2. [Download the Workflow Files](#)
3. [Fetch Singularity Images](#)
4. [Run the Workflow](#)
 - 4a. [Approach 1: Run the workflow on a GeneLab RNAseq dataset with automatic retrieval of Ensembl reference fasta and gtf files](#)
 - 4b. [Approach 2: Run the workflow on a GeneLab RNAseq dataset using local Ensembl reference fasta and gtf files](#)
 - 4c. [Approach 3: Run the workflow on a non-GLDS dataset using a user-created runsheet](#)
5. [Additional Output Files](#)

